

INFORMATICS RESEARCH EVALUATION, 2025 REVISED REPORT

An Informatics Europe report
endorsed by National Informatics Association members of
Informatics Europe

Informatics Research Evaluation, 2025 Revised Report

An Informatics Europe Report

Prepared by *the Research Evaluation Recommendations Panel* of Informatics Europe. Endorsed by National Informatics Associations of Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

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Executive Summary

Evaluation is an indispensable instrument for improving research quality and impact. To achieve the intended effects, research evaluation should follow established and widely accepted principles, be benchmarked against appropriate criteria, and be sensitive to disciplinary differences. This report addresses the principles and criteria that are to be followed when individual researchers are evaluated for their research in the field of Informatics.

This report builds on and updates the outcomes of the 2008 and 2018 *Informatics Europe reports on Research Evaluation for Computer Science/Informatics*, while aligning its recommendations with other recent documents on research evaluation, most notably the *CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA 2022)*. The report also contains updated analyses and recommendations in four topical areas of concern in Informatics: the responsible use of bibliometrics and credit assignment in contributions, assessing artefacts, Open Science, and interdisciplinary research, together with a discussion on the role of AI in research evaluation.

Our key messages are the following:

1. Informatics is an original discipline that combines aspects of mathematics, science, and engineering. Researcher evaluation must recognise and respect its specificity.
2. A distinctive feature of publication in Informatics is the importance of highly selective conferences. Journals have complementary advantages but do not necessarily carry more prestige. Publication models that couple conferences and journals, where the papers of a conference are published directly in a journal, are a growing trend that may bridge the current gap between these two forms of publishing.
3. Open archives and overlay journals are recent innovations in the Informatics publication culture that offer improved tracking in evaluation.
4. The impact of artefacts such as software, open datasets, and other research products such as trained machine learning models can be as great as publications. The evaluation of such objects, which is now conducted by many conferences, should be encouraged and accepted as an established component of research assessment. Another important indicator of impact is advances that lead to commercial exploitation or adoption by industry or standardisation bodies.
5. Open Science and its research evaluation practices are highly relevant to Informatics. Informatics has played a key enabling role in the Open Science revolution and should remain at its forefront.
6. Numerical measurements such as citation and publication counts must never be used as the sole evaluation instrument. They must be filtered through human interpretation, specifically to avoid errors, and complemented by peer review and assessment of outputs other than publications. In particular, numerical measurements must not be used to compare researchers across scientific disciplines, including across subfields of Informatics.
7. In Informatics, the order of authors often holds little significance and varies across subfields. Without clear guidelines, it should not be a factor in researcher evaluation. Instead, authors should be encouraged to clearly state the scope and role of their individual contributions to multi-author works.
8. In assessing institutions, researchers, publications, and citations, the use of open research information provided by Open Science infrastructures should be favoured and supported. When using ranking and benchmarking services provided by for-profit companies, respect for open access criteria is mandatory. Journal-based or journal-biased ranking services are inadequate for most of Informatics and must not be used.
9. Any evaluation, especially quantitative, must be based on clear, published criteria. Furthermore, assessment criteria must themselves undergo assessment and revision.
10. Any use of generative AI in research evaluation should increase the quality of the assessments and reduce the effort of the human evaluators. AI must not be used to reduce the number of human experts in assessment panels and their collective responsibility for the panels' recommendations.

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1. Research Evaluation

Evaluation is innately linked with research. The work of researchers is subject to evaluation from the very beginning of their careers. Research results submitted for assessment are subject to a peer review process that scrutinises their scientific quality and potential for impact. The researchers themselves are constantly being evaluated: for recruitment, for promotion, for funding of research proposals, when being considered for specific roles in committees, for recognition by awards, etc. Researchers also often act as evaluators of their peers.

By and large, these evaluation processes are internal to the research community and aim to guarantee its internal fairness and integrity through self-regulation. Increasingly, evaluation is also mandated and regulated by exogenous entities and scaled from individuals to entire institutions. In many cases, governments have developed national evaluation standards and processes. Often, their end results are institutional rankings. The main motivation for these efforts is to guarantee that taxpayers' money is spent on research efficiently and leads to societal benefits.

Research evaluation can thus be performed for different goals. It can target a specific piece of research (documented by a single or several artefacts), an individual researcher, a research group, or an organisational unit (e.g., a department). It may even generalise to entire institutions (e.g., universities) or even countries. In any case, the goal of evaluation is to assess some explicit or implicit notion of value, or quality, of research. To achieve the positive objectives of research evaluation, **the specific goals of any such evaluation effort must be clearly stated**, and the way it is conducted must be aligned with these goals. The **evaluation must follow established principles and practical criteria, known and shared by evaluators and researchers**, and **take into account any specificities of the scientific field and area involved**.

Evaluation can have a tremendously positive effect in improving research quality and productivity. It is vital to recognise and support research that can lead to advances in knowledge and impact on society. At the same time, **the effect of following ill-conceived criteria or practices in research evaluation, or misusing metrics and indicators, can have seriously negative long-term effects.** In particular, it may greatly damage the potential of future generations of researchers. Furthermore, **very frequent evaluation can have a detrimental effect on fundamental research**, as the assessment may then accentuate low-risk, short-term developments at the expense of potentially high-gain, long-term work.

This report focuses on the main **principles and criteria that should be followed when individual researchers¹ are evaluated** for their research activity **in the field of Informatics²**, addressing the specificities of this area. This subsumes the evaluation of a specific piece of research and can, to some extent, be generalised to departments since their research performance is largely determined by their individuals.

This report reasserts the recommendations in previous Informatics Europe reports on the subject (Informatics Europe 2008, 2018), to which it incorporates a number of observations concerning the topical areas of bibliometrics and credit assignment in contributions, assessing artefacts, Open Science, interdisciplinary research, and the role of AI in research evaluation.

An important development since the publication of the 2018 report has been the convergence of several reports and initiatives on revising research evaluation practices into the *CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment* (CoARA 2022). The recommendations in this report have been reviewed and updated to align with the CoARA recommendations.

¹ Some aspects of department evaluation are addressed in the publication (Informatics Europe 2013).

² Interchangeably "Computer Science" or "Computing".

2. Informatics and Its Specificity

2.1 Characteristics of Informatics

Informatics is a relatively **young science** that is **rapidly evolving** in close connection with technology.

Beyond the two basic and universal research pillars of theory and experimentation, which in Informatics research are often both present in varying proportions, a third important component in Informatics is the creation of **artefacts**, which provide new designs, tools or otherwise improved support for information processing tasks.

Informatics research covers an extremely wide and **methodologically diverse** family of areas: from the development of new computing devices to the mathematical theory of algorithms and complexity, from human factors to big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence, from studies of programmers' productivity to secure encryption methods. Interdisciplinarity, as in the case of bioinformatics, medical informatics, geo-informatics, or cognitive science, brings in even more diversity.

With the continuing digitalisation of society and the emergence of potentially disruptive computational technologies such as artificial intelligence and quantum computing, Informatics has an **extremely high societal and economic impact**. Measuring up to these responsibilities not only requires continuous progress in Informatics research, but also calls for more emphasis on Informatics education and the influence of Informatics on society, including ethical concerns.

Research in Informatics, as in any other science, must be evaluated according to criteria that take into account the field's specificity. Universal criteria do not exist for evaluating research quality. This is also true for the different subfields of Informatics. Differences between fields must be taken into account, and the temptation to adopt simplistic, one-size-fits-all criteria should be resisted.

2.2 The Informatics publication culture and its evolution

The publication culture within Informatics differs from most other fields in the **prominent role played by conference publications**. Many subfields of Informatics have leading conferences with status, visibility, and impact comparable to or higher than their respective leading journals. Conference papers at these meetings undergo a highly selective peer-review process that makes these venues very competitive and often leads to lower acceptance rates than in the best journals. Conferences in Informatics provide a faster turnaround time than journals to publish research results, get feedback from peers and build upon it, and also often have higher standards of novelty than journals. These factors are crucial in a rapidly evolving field like Informatics, and as a result, in Informatics, **journals do not necessarily carry more prestige** than conferences. Journal publications are, of course, also important, especially for gathering and reworking antecedent research into an archival presentation that is carefully prepared, has guaranteed long-term availability, and is free of the space limitations imposed by conferences.

Towards bridging the dichotomy between conferences and journals, new alternatives are now changing the publication culture:

- **Coupled conferences and journals**, implemented in different ways: VLDB-style with continuous submission to the journal and presentation of the accepted papers at the conference; ICLP-style with the proceedings of the conference being published as a special issue of a standard journal (in this case TPLP); and its variant PACMPL-style,³ where a dedicated journal is used to publish

³ VLDB: "International Journal on Very Large Databases"; ICLP: "International Conference on Logic Programming"; TPLP: "Journal on Theory and Practice of Logic Programming"; PACMPL: "Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages".

proceedings of several different, related conferences. These hybrid combinations of conferences and journals are a **promising and growing trend** that combines the advantages of timely publication of conferences with the impact tracking of journals (Dagstuhl 2012).

- **Open Archives** (arXiv, HAL, Zenodo etc.) provide opportunities to publish first versions of papers and protect intellectual property of new results, at the same time giving online access to all proofs and materials, including data and software, that sustain these results. After possible feedback from peers, improved versions can be submitted to **overlay journals** according to their publication constraints. In this model, reviewers have access to the complete history of the results and can better evaluate their quality and impact.

Books remain a specific and important format for providing a comprehensive view of a given topic and for contributing to education. Here again, prepublication in an open archive can help in sharing drafts, getting feedback from peers before official publication, managing versions, etc.

Another specificity of the Informatics publishing culture is that unlike in other sciences, such as Physics or Medicine, Informatics does not have a generally adopted convention for interpreting the order in which the authors of a publication are listed, and does not especially distinguish the “corresponding author(s)”. Thus, in the absence of specific indications, author order should not serve as a factor in individual researchers’ evaluations. This issue is discussed more extensively in Section 4 of this report.

3. Research Evaluation for Increased Quality and Impact

The fundamental goal of research evaluation is to assess the quality and impact of research for the eventual improvement of both. **Quality** is an elusive intrinsic characteristic for which a commonly accepted assessment method, even if imperfect, is peer review by a panel of informed experts. **Impact** is an observable external characteristic that takes many forms and can to some extent be measured by numerical indicators, but even then, **only with human expert interpretation**. Quality is mostly a good predictor of impact, and impact is mostly a good indicator of quality, but the two are not coextensive. The CoARA agreement recommends to “focus research assessment criteria on quality [and] recognise the contributions that advance knowledge and the (potential) impact of research results” (CoARA 2022, p. 3). Assessing impact can be quite difficult, and is often even infeasible in a short timeframe, because the impact of a body of research can be indirect and it may take years before the eventual impact can be recognised.

3.1 Assessing the quality of research

As recognised by the CoARA agreement, “research assessment should rely primarily on qualitative assessment for which peer review is central, supported by responsibly used quantitative indicators where appropriate” and “it is important that peer review processes are designed to meet the fundamental principles of rigour and transparency” (CoARA 2022, p. 5).

With the increasing availability of publicly available bibliometric data, research assessments have been resorting more and more to bibliometric indicators provided by a variety of sources, often even without questioning the sources’ soundness and trustability. While we acknowledge the usefulness of quantitative data and bibliometric indicators when used responsibly (see Section 4), we emphasise the following:

Research assessment should not take quantity as a proxy for quality and impact (cf. Friedman & Schneider 2015). Any policy that tends to favour quantity over quality has potentially disruptive effects and can mislead young researchers with very negative long-term effects. Such policies can lead researchers to focus on publishing the least publishable increments, and in this respect, some European countries have established national evaluation practices with indicators that raise serious concerns. To stress the importance of quality and impact, researcher evaluations should preferably focus on a relatively small number of high-quality publications and artefacts, trying to identify also their impact carriers such as novelty, supporting artefacts, and influence on other researchers' work.

Quantitative data and bibliometric indicators must be interpreted in the specific context of the research being evaluated. They should never constitute the sole evaluation criterion. Different research areas and even subfields of Informatics have very different characteristics. Even within a homogeneous set, bibliometric indicators only provide a very coarse assessment. For example, although a very high number of citations may indicate a potentially impactful piece of work, it may also indicate a widely referenced survey rather than a novel original contribution (which, of course, also has its own value). **Human appraisal with respect to established criteria is needed to interpret data and discern quality and impact.** Numbers can only help; they are not a substitute.

In addition to being established, known, and shared by evaluators and researchers, **assessment criteria must themselves undergo assessment and revision** in order to follow the evolution of science.

Other indicators for quality

Major conferences and scholarly societies in Informatics often grant "best paper awards" to contributions perceived to have the highest value of those accepted at a conference. A further development is the granting of "most influential paper" or "test-of-time" awards for contributions perceived to have had the most influence in the area over some past number of years. These distinguishing, peer-reviewed awards should be taken into account in evaluations.

3.2 Assessing the impact of research

The impact of research can be assessed along many different dimensions. First, one can distinguish between external and community impact. The **external impact** of research concerns its effect on society at large. The new GenAI techniques, for example, will potentially have an enormous impact on society. Likewise, the invention of a new secure protocol may lead to the development of more secure networks on which society relies, and a new automated development environment can improve the industry's productivity. Advances that lead to commercial exploitation, spin-off activities, or adoption by industry (e.g., software licenses) or standardisation bodies, are some highly valued indicators of external impact. **Community impact**, on the other hand, refers to the impact of one's research on other researchers. This means that other researchers can build on top of one's research. Evaluation often tries to capture this kind of impact by, e.g., citation indices or research software download counts. A different kind of indicator could be provided by software competitions that are regularly organised to assess progress in tools (e.g., SAT solvers or learning tools). Such competitions are typically highly appreciated and contribute to increasing the quality of the tools, and success in them could be taken as an indicator, or at least a predictor, of community impact.

An orthogonal dimension of impact concerns the outcomes of research. An outcome can have an impact because it advances **knowledge** in a given area or because it advances **practice**. New *knowledge* can be created by theoretical research, similar to mathematics. A typical example is research on algorithms and computational complexity. New knowledge can also be generated by research that pursues empirical

studies using tools from Informatics, sometimes also addressing Informatics itself. Typical examples are discovering properties of biological systems or physical materials using machine learning techniques, or the automatic extraction of interaction patterns among software designers from open-source repositories. Advances in *practice*, on the other hand, refer to research that aims at developing new tools or methods to solve a given problem. Examples of this would be, for instance, a novel machine learning method for brain tumor detection from magnetic resonance images, or a new mathematical or computational technique that improves the scalability of program verification software.

4. Responsible Use of Indicators and Credit Assignment in Contributions

The most common method of evaluating research impact is through citations. Counting citations is often viewed as a way to gauge a publication's influence within the research community. This approach has been extended into various bibliometric indicators, such as the h-index for researchers and various impact factor measures for publication venues. Because bibliometric measures have gained popularity under the pressure of external evaluation, and publishing companies have readily added them to their offers to the community, they are commonly, and often tacitly, used in internal evaluations that claim to rely on peer review. However, bibliometrics must always be complemented by qualitative peer review that focuses on the research content and approaches measuring contributions beyond publications.

Responsible use of numerical indicators for assessing research should abide by the following recommendations:

R4.1 Publication counts, whether weighted or not, must not be used to evaluate research value. While they may measure productivity, they are not indicators of research impact or quality.

R4.2 Numerical impact measurements, such as citation counts, must not be used in isolation. They must be interpreted by humans, taking into account the potential for errors and unethical practices, such as “gaming the system”.

R4.3 Such indicators also must not be used to compare researchers across different fields, or across subfields of Informatics, due to the varying publication and citation cultures.

This is in line with the CoARA recommendation to “base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators” (CoARA 2022, p. 5).

It is also important to assess the individual contributions in multi-author publications. In some disciplines, the order of authorship reflects the level of contribution, but this is often not the case in Informatics, even though Informatics researchers also face the necessity to produce publications with “primary authorship” roles, particularly for publication-based PhDs. In these contexts, even the percentages of authors' contributions are sometimes assessed and documented. To address this, we recommend that researchers clearly specify each author's contribution in their publications and other scientific artefacts to facilitate fair evaluation. The CRediT taxonomy (<https://credit.niso.org>) provides one structured way of documenting contributions across the roles of Conceptualisation, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualisation, Writing – original draft, and Writing – review & editing. In line with CRediT guidelines, we suggest that all contributions be listed, whether from authors or individuals acknowledged elsewhere. Individual contributors can be assigned multiple roles, and a single role can be assigned to multiple contributors. Where multiple individuals serve in the same role, the degree of contribution can optionally be specified as ‘lead,’ ‘equal,’ or ‘supporting.’

(<https://credit.niso.org/implementing-credit/>, 2024-07-29). If the CRediT taxonomy does not seem to fit, it is suggested to use another one or invent roles appropriate for the artefact in question. In any case, transparency in this regard is of the highest value for both evaluators and the researchers themselves.

When harvesting bibliometric data, public databases such as ArXiv, DBLP, HAL, and Zenodo are valuable because they offer low-noise data on publications and often provide full-text access. DBLP makes available very useful accounts of the Informatics publications of individual researchers. Most currently available bibliometric analysis tools, however, are inadequate for Informatics, because they are either journal-based, journal-biased, or not well curated. The widely used Clarivate bibliometric tools, for instance, mostly address journal publications, and while Elsevier Scopus provides also some coverage of conferences, it is still journal-biased. To complement these resources, ICORE (<https://www.core.edu.au/icore-portal>) and CSRankings (<https://csrankings.org>) provide informative rankings of conferences and institutions, similar to those furnished by Clarivate JCR and Scopus SJR for journals, but have their own biases. (Particularly CSRankings is quite myopically focused on a small list of “top conferences”, to the exclusion of everything else.) Google Scholar is inclusive of all kinds of data sources and thus more aligned with the Informatics publication culture, but suffers from high data noise.

While quantitative bibliometric indicators can provide insights into global trends at institutional levels, they can have only a supportive role in assessing individual researchers or projects. Furthermore, prominent indicators such as the h-index are prone to manipulation, such as by using citation rings or paid authorship positions.

Evaluating individual contributions requires contextualising them within the standards and best practices of the specific field, which can only be effectively done by peers with domain expertise. Even though peer review is inherently subjective, collective assessments by expert panels impart robustness to the process, and indicators can provide useful additional insight in this context. The value of quantitative indicators is highly questionable unless they are contextualised and explained appropriately.

For properly assigning individual credit in contributions, we recommend the following practices:

R4.4 Clearly Specify Individual Contributions. Researchers should explicitly detail each author's contributions in publications and scientific artefacts to enable fair evaluation, including contributions from non-authors, if present. Transparency in documenting contributions is of utmost importance, benefiting both evaluators and researchers by enabling more accurate and equitable assessments.

R4.5 Use Standardised or Context-Appropriate Taxonomies. Authors should adopt established frameworks like the CRediT taxonomy to classify contributions by roles. If such taxonomies seem unsuitable, researchers should develop or adapt roles appropriate to the specific artefact.

R4.6 Provide Granular Detail Where Necessary. Contributions can be further clarified by specifying the degree of involvement when multiple contributors share the same role, ensuring nuanced understanding of individual input.

5. Assessing Artefacts

In this section, we explore the evaluation of research using outputs that go beyond traditional publications, such as software and other outcomes. While our primary focus will be on software, many of the points discussed are likely applicable also to other research outputs. These may include datasets, collections of theorems to test automated theorem provers, formal specifications, proofs developed with interactive provers, complex build environments, RTL definitions of processors, microcode, and similar results.

5.1 Software artefacts

“Software artefacts” submitted alongside publications (Winter 2022) are now routinely evaluated in Informatics conferences. These artefacts serve as evidence to support the claims made in the papers by enabling the reproduction of the results therein. They should include detailed installation instructions or be provided as a container or virtual machine image for ease of use. These artefacts are immutable snapshots, ideally stored in established repositories that offer long-term preservation (e.g., Zenodo, FigShare, Software Heritage) or in infrastructures following ongoing data and software preservation proposals (e.g., FAIR Digital Objects, RO-Crate, or the Research Data Management Container from the NFDIxCS project). Quality “badges” may be awarded based on factors such as ease of installation, functionality, and how effectively the artefacts reproduce the results presented in the publication. Many Informatics conferences and societies provide detailed guidelines for this evaluation process (ACM, 2020; Rous, 2017).

It is important to note that reproducibility is not only relevant for conferences but is also a fundamental pillar of Open Science, as defined by UNESCO (UNESCO 2021 a, UNESCO 2021 b). Reproducibility issues in sub-areas such as AI and machine learning are impacting other scientific disciplines that rely on their outcomes (Ball 2023; Baker 2016). Of course, no subfield of computer science is free from these concerns, and therefore the growing adoption of artefact evaluation is laudable.

However, the academic value of these artefacts is tied to that of the associated publication. Their evaluation primarily confirms that the artefact aligns with the expectations set by the publication. As a result, their pertinence as independently assessed research outcomes is not clear. Additionally, these artefacts are typically not expected to evolve over time by incorporating additional functionality or improving performance, and, therefore, the evaluation guidelines are not expected to take into account long-term preservation.

Efforts to ensure that artefact evaluation is as fair and rigorous as possible are ongoing. For instance, the International Association for Cryptologic Research (IACR) has established a task force to standardise, across the conferences it sponsors, guidelines and practices which until now have largely been determined by conference chairs and steering committees. Additionally, the USENIX Security Conference will introduce a new topic in 2025, “Meta-Science in Security and Privacy”, which will include reports and studies on the replicability—or failure to replicate—of previously reported research results (USENIX 2025).

On the other hand, some software packages / systems are designed with the expectation of continuous evolution and improvement, incorporating additional functionalities over time. These packages often result from long-term collaborative efforts involving multiple researchers and developers. Some examples (among many others) include systems like Coq and CVC, which are extensively used in their respective fields.

These systems are often not associated with a single publication and, as such, cannot be classified as usual “artefacts”. The techniques and ideas they implement may be described across multiple publications, but some key components of these systems may not be documented in any publication. Yet, they can represent significant research contributions and demonstrate an innovative use of technology. This raises the question of how to properly recognise and reward the effort involved in developing and maintaining such systems.

5.2 Why evaluate software systems

A strong argument for evaluating software systems as independent, standalone research contributions is that their authors deserve recognition for the significant resources and effort invested in the

development and maintenance of these systems, which play a crucial role in advancing science. This reasoning can also be applied to other types of research outputs, such as those (partially) listed before. Therefore, we understand that to assess impact, research software and datasets are as important as publications.

Large, robust software systems that implement complex techniques are continuously used by researchers other than their original authors. Systems like Coq and CVC, previously mentioned, are examples of influential software packages. In the domain of datasets, “Thousands of Problems for Theorem Provers” (TPTP) serves as a key resource. TPTP is regularly used by theorem prover developers to evaluate the efficiency of their systems and make fair comparisons. Although the “deep knowledge” gained from collecting and categorising such examples may seem modest, the contribution to advancing the field of theorem proving must be acknowledged.

By releasing robust, well-engineered, and useful systems and/or curated datasets, authors provide essential building blocks upon which more advanced research can be conducted. This creates a global benefit for both academia and society that hopefully pays off for the resources invested in the design, implementation, and maintenance of these systems.

On the other hand, well-engineered software systems and datasets are also an integral part of the Open Science ecosystem, which includes “open research data, open software, source code, and open hardware”. These resources lower the barrier for technologically inclined but not-yet-proficient-enough individuals, such as a first-year computer science student who may lack the skills to install complex software with dependencies and intricate configurations, to explore and better understand the outcomes of research funded by society.

5.3 Caveats

Developing a software system according to sound software engineering practices requires significantly more effort than making an artefact available.⁴ However, researchers often lack the funding to hire skilled software engineers, programmers, and, when needed, data scientists or other specialised professionals. As a result, they must allocate their own time and resources, diverting focus from their primary research. Furthermore, maintaining such systems demands substantial resources.

In the current state of affairs, there is little incentive to develop well-rounded, high-quality software systems. This creates a vicious cycle: because software systems are not inherently valued, minimal effort is invested in demonstrating the feasibility of certain techniques, resulting in software that may be of only average quality. The subpar quality, in turn, diminishes interest in using the software, as it may be difficult to use, leading to projects being abandoned for lack of impact. From a broader perspective, this represents a misuse of resources that ultimately harms both the academic community and society at large. Rather than rewarding authors who maintain and improve software systems, the current research evaluation system penalises them, as the time and resources dedicated to these systems often come at the expense of traditional publication-based research, which is commonly recognised.

This may be partly because there are specific characteristics – particularly from a software engineering perspective – that need to be assessed in software but are not relevant to publications. An incomplete list of key aspects to consider in software evaluation includes:

- **Longevity and evolution:** Software systems are long-lived and undergo complex evolution. Properly accounting for this and distinguishing between genuine research contributions and routine engineering updates can be challenging.

⁴ This is not meant to minimise the challenges of preparing artefacts, but rather to highlight the clear reality that as systems increase in size and complexity, so do the difficulties of development and maintenance.

- **Authorship:** Assigning ownership to specific functionalities or implementations of algorithms can be difficult. However, this challenge is not unique to software: it also occurs with multi-author publications. A suggestion for handling authorship in publications is provided in Section 4, and a practical approach for software systems has been implemented by INRIA (Canteaut 2021).
- **Measuring impact:** Metrics such as the number of users or downloads, often used as proxies for a software’s relevance or usefulness, can be difficult to estimate accurately or may be artificially inflated. Furthermore, these metrics may not always reflect the true impact on the research community or the quality of the software.
- **Temporal context:** Evaluating a software system or its characteristics long after its initial development can be problematic, as the motivations and significance of the software at the time of its creation may be hard to fully appreciate.
- **Industry collaborations:** In cases of industry collaboration, software may be subject to usage restrictions, limitations on functionality, or restricted access to source code, making it difficult to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of its merits.

5.4 Recommendations

There is currently no universally accepted policy for evaluating independent software systems. Even in the case of publications, where established quality indicators exist (the relevance of conferences or journals, community impact through e.g. citations, and expert evaluations), different institutions and countries apply varying approaches. Given the challenges outlined above, we are unable to provide concrete recommendations for evaluating software systems at this time. Instead, we offer some general recommendations and considerations that should be taken into account to make evaluations as fair as possible. Additionally, a comprehensive framework would need to address not only software but also datasets, open hardware definitions, and other related outputs.

R5.1 Avoid “bean counting”: Evaluations should not rely solely on quantitative metrics such as lines of code, number of projects, or downloads. While these metrics can provide useful insights, they should not be the primary or dominant source of information.

R5.2 No penalty for lack of software releases: Researchers with strong traditional publication-based research records should not be penalised for not releasing software. While this is a reasonable principle, its implementation in environments with limited positions and promotions remains a challenge.

R5.3 Reward only research-driven software advancements: Only software developments that generate new knowledge or research should be rewarded. Improvements demonstrating engineering skills but lacking a research component should not count toward research evaluation. For instance, maintaining a large system, although resource-intensive, should not be considered part of research evaluation.

R5.4 Long-term software projects deserve recognition: Software systems that have been in use and actively maintained over decades should be considered particularly significant achievements.

R5.5 Consider the researcher’s role: The role of a researcher in a software project should be factored into the evaluation, similar to the way author roles are classified in research publications, as discussed elsewhere in this report.

R5.6 Short contributions: Short contributions to large projects should count toward research evaluation only when they add a key component or capability that significantly enhances the project, and this enhancement comes from a real scientific advance and not because of a mere engineering task.

R5.7 Cumulative value of successful artefacts: A continuous record of successfully evaluated artefacts, even if they are not part of a large system, can be seen as having a cumulative value greater than the sum

of individual publications or artefacts. This demonstrates a sustained commitment to validating the practicality of research ideas.

R5.8 Value of contributions to components: Contributions to components of larger systems (e.g., libraries, parts of compilers) should be valued independently, as they provide essential functionality for other researchers or to perform advanced training (at the level of PhD, for example). For example, contributions to systems like LLVM or Coq may be more valuable than creating a standalone toy compiler.

R5.9 Weigh software releases appropriately: Not all public releases of software should be weighed equally. Evaluation should focus on the changes introduced between releases. Alternatively, the latest version could be the focus of the evaluation rather than treating each release with the same importance.

R5.10 Citing software: Software used in research must be properly cited. While it is common to cite the publication where the software is presented, if a specific version of the software has been used in some research work (especially if it includes functionality not covered by any publication), the contributors to that version should be appropriately credited. This requires the use of permanent, immutable identifiers associated with the software version and with its authors. An example of an existing proposal that is used in practice is the persistent identifier provided by Software Heritage (Di Cosmo, Gruenpeter, and Zacchiroli, 2020) and used, for example, in HAL (Di Cosmo, 2019).

R5.11 Public software for public funding: Software developed with public funding should be openly accessible to ensure transparency and accountability, especially when it is subject to evaluation.

R5.12 Specific software evaluation criteria: There is a need for distinct criteria to evaluate software. According to an internal study by the software subcommittee of the French National Committee for Open Science, the FAIR principles used for datasets are not easily adaptable to software, and specific metrics must be devised for effective evaluation.

The protocol established by INRIA (Canteaut 2021) for evaluating software systems may be one of the better-defined ones. It involves a self-evaluation of software contributions, which is then reviewed by a committee. The self-assessment form and evaluation guidelines could serve as a valuable starting point for replication or adoption in other institutions and agencies. Along these lines, the French Ministry of Research and Education annually gives awards to outstanding software developed for education or research purposes or created in a scientific context; expanding such awards to a European level could be beneficial. Additionally, and in a related category, Italian universities are evaluated based on societal impact, a criterion that could also encompass well-maintained academic software systems.

6. Open Science

In the past ten years, Open Science has become one of the most topical issues in the scholarly domain at large. Open Science comprises a plethora of different dimensions which aim at incentivising quality in science and recognising the diversity of research outputs, activities, and missions. However, Open Science is not a granted state of affairs, but it is the result of a community effort that pushes to develop an appropriate policy environment to host it in the scholarly ecosystem. Part of this environment concerns also “research and researcher evaluation and assessment practices” (UNESCO 2021).

When discussing and debating about how research is conducted, this “construct” (UNESCO 2021) also concerns how research should be evaluated. UNESCO emphasises the importance of rewarding, in assessment processes, good open science practices – a necessary incentive for enabling the implementation and operationalisation of Open Science. This also fosters a revision of the current

research assessment practices to align them with the principles of Open Science. Indeed, the overall direction suggested is to build assessment processes on existing and well-known practices and guidelines – such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA 2012), the Leiden Manifesto (Hick et al. 2015), and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA 2022). The main action points of these guidelines are:

- Avoid using metrics developed for measuring one kind of entity (e.g. Journal Impact Factor for journals) as a proxy measure for assessing other kinds of entities (e.g. researchers).
- Make explicit the criteria used in the assessment, and prefer peer-review evaluation, supported by quantitative indicators when appropriate – as discussed in detail earlier in Sections 4 and 5.
- Recognise the diversity of research contributions in assessment exercises (datasets, databases, software, and other artefacts), in addition to classic print-like publications (journal articles, books, book chapters, etc.) – as largely discussed in Section 5.
- Apply openness and transparency when providing data and methods used in the assessment exercise.
- Enable anyone to verify both the data and the analysis.
- Fight against manipulations and incorrect uses of metrics – as anticipated in Section 4.
- Consider the variability of different types of research output and subject areas when comparing an entity against another entity (e.g. researchers).
- Focus on qualitative judgement of research outputs when assessing researchers – as discussed in Section 4.

Several of these actions are not implementable without the availability of appropriate Open Science infrastructures such as open bibliographic and citation databases and metadata repositories, institutional research information systems, and open bibliometrics and scientometrics systems for assessing and analysing scientific domains. Indeed, UNESCO insists that investing in Open Science infrastructures and services is essential, and that the scholarly community should retain control and ownership over these infrastructures. They are a crucial means for providing the data, i.e., research information used for devising metrics and indicators that may be used to support peer-review assessment.

Research information refers to all the metadata related to the conduct and communication of research, such as bibliographic metadata of research outcomes (articles, software, datasets, methodologies, etc.), information on funding and grants, and information on organisations and research contributors. Several initiatives, such as the Barcelona Declaration (DORI 2024), and several Open Science infrastructures push for making research information openly available and freely reusable for the scholarly community because various activities, including research assessment, are characterised by using such information. Among the relevant infrastructures, OpenCitations (<https://opencitations.net>), OpenAIRE (<https://openaire.eu>), Software Heritage (<https://www.softwareheritage.org>), and DBLP (<https://dblp.org>) also provide information about software and other Informatics-related artefacts in addition to classic publications in journals and conference proceedings. Other infrastructures, such as PRereview (<https://prereview.org>), help in addressing related assessment tasks in a very transparent way, e.g. by enabling open peer review practices. These open reviewing processes permit the disclosure of the identity of the reviewers, the publication of reviews, and thus, the recognition of the effort that scholars put into reviewing, and the possibility for a broader community to provide comments and participate in the assessment process (UNESCO 2021).

Supporting these kinds of Open Science and community-guided infrastructures is key to maintaining an environment that enables transparent assessment workflows. Indeed, there is an urgent need to make research information to advance responsible research assessment and operationalise Open Science and promote unbiased, transparent, and high-quality decision-making. The Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM) (European Commission 2017) represents a possible, practical move toward a more comprehensive approach to evaluating researchers through the lens of Open Science. In addition, other

templates for Open Science assessment that involve Informatics as a domain of application have been studied in the context of specific research projects, such as GraspOS (<https://graspos.eu/>).

Informatics should **acknowledge Open Science practices** in its research evaluation. Informatics thus also has a prominent role to play in the adoption and development of the Open Science approaches and infrastructures, and its support is key to keep them sustainable in the long term.

R6.1 Acknowledge, support, and adopt Open Science practices in Informatics.

R6.2 Apply principles derived from Open Science practices in the evaluation of research.

R6.3 Strive to keep the control of Open Science infrastructures and processes within the research, academic, and educational Informatics communities.

7. Interdisciplinary Research

Informatics has for a long time been an important support provider for research in other fields, in the form of software tools for modelling, optimisation and visualisation, data management and analysis, etc. In an interdisciplinary collaboration this kind of work is often considered mundane by the companion area partners, and not really computing research by the Informatics community. And indeed, for instance simply applying a known analysis method to a new dataset without a clear scientific advance on the Informatics side is just a technical support task.

There are however also more ambitious collaborations, where the Informatics contribution is an integral element of the research agenda, and pursuing it requires both competence in the companion area and an ability to adapt existing and develop new methods in Informatics for the needs of the specific collaboration. A high-profile example of the latter kind of collaboration is e.g. the work on computational protein design that was awarded one of the 2024 Nobel Prizes in Chemistry. Even in such cases, however, credit is commonly assigned along disciplinary lines, so that recognition goes primarily to the companion area, and also on the Informatics side the computational methods contribution is considered as “an application”.

An added challenge is that in assessments that are based mechanically on publication venues and/or indicators, Informatics contributions to other areas than core Informatics are easily overlooked, because the relevant venues are either not indexed at all in Informatics databases, or are considered as “application area outlets”, no matter how prestigious in the companion area.

The challenge of overcoming disciplinary barriers in the assessment of integrative interdisciplinary research is a widely recognised problem (e.g. McLeish & Strang 2016). Some key recommendations for the responsible evaluation of Informatics research in this context are:

R7.1 Recognise the value of integrated interdisciplinary research in its own terms, not as an “application” of Informatics.

R7.2 Assess (i) the depth of the integration and (ii) the novelty and significance of the Informatics contribution to the totality of the work.

R7.3 Be wary of numerical indicators and “top venue” lists oriented towards assessing Informatics disciplinary work (such as e.g. the CSRankings conference list).

8. The Role of AI in Research Evaluations

The emergence of powerful AI methods and tools influences research evaluation in two ways: first, how to regard and assess AI being used in research, and second, how AI can be used to perform or assist in carrying out research evaluations. While the first point is being intensely discussed, much less discussion exists regarding the second point. We shall address the latter issue here.

Whenever a task is tedious, the question arises of how it can be automated or at least made easier by delegating parts to an automated process. A good example in the context of research evaluations is the h-index, which is widely used but also heavily criticised. Its advantage lies in the ease with which it can be obtained. It is much harder to judge the content of publications than simply count them and their citation numbers. Until now, there was no easy way to delegate the refereeing of publications to an automated process. This has changed with the advent of Large Language Models (LLMs). It is certainly tempting to use such models to evaluate the output of researchers or entire departments (or even universities). At the time of writing this position publication, the generally available LLMs are hesitant to write entire evaluations. For example, Gemini primarily describes the process of writing an evaluation but does not provide one. ChatGPT can write an evaluation but is very cautious in comparing different Informatics departments. Moreover, ChatGPT bases its judgments on citation numbers and very vague identification of key strengths.

Nevertheless, we can safely assume that LLMs can, in principle, be used for research evaluations and that they will be used for this purpose in the future, if not already today. The question for us is to understand the potential dangers and benefits of this development.

As with any other use of AI, some might call for restrictions or an outright ban on using AI methods in evaluations that form the basis of important decisions, such as funding large projects or granting tenure. It is short-sighted to ban AI altogether: it might actually help in the decision-making process when used with discretion, and a ban cannot be enforced anyway. Rather than a ban, we recommend the following policies for the responsible use of such technologies, if they are used at all:

R8.1 The use of generative AI in research evaluations should be communicated openly, including detailed logs of the communications and the way the information was used in the decision-making.

R8.2 Decisions must still be made by human experts, and the use of AI should be restricted to the lower levels of the decision process.

R8.3 Efforts should be made to verify critical data obtained from a computer.

R8.4 The use of AI must not be used to reduce the number of human experts in decision panels and their responsibility for the outcome of the panel.

The use of AI is a moving target, and today we are just beginning to harness its power. While AI has been instrumental in many areas for some time, its applications in decision-making are still in their early stages. Research evaluation is among these areas, and further discussions in the near future will be important as the field continues to evolve. Therefore, our conclusions at this time can only be considered preliminary.

9. Conclusions

Research evaluation is essential for maintaining the vigour of any scientific field, and the system of expectations and incentives created by evaluation practices can have a significant effect on a research field's development. Informatics has many special characteristics, including methodological diversity, close connection between topical research and socio-economic impact, prominence of top conferences as primary publication venues, artefacts as first-class research outcomes, etc. These may not always be apparent from outside of the field, yet need special consideration when assessing research in Informatics. In a judicious evaluation process, these specificities must be taken into account, together with the general principles of responsible research evaluation as advanced in, e.g., the CoARA recommendations.

In this document, we are reconfirming and updating the general guidelines for Informatics research evaluation presented in the 2008 and 2018 Informatics Europe reports on the topic. We are also providing analyses and recommendations in some areas that were previously treated in less detail or have increased in prominence since the preparation of the earlier reports: bibliometrics and credit assignment in contributions, assessing artefacts, Open Science, interdisciplinary research, and the role of AI in research evaluation. As with any other aspects of science and research, the dynamic and changing landscape will certainly warrant revisiting these recommendations again in some years, especially as pertains to topics that are relatively recent.

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Endorsements

This report is endorsed by the following [National Informatics Association members](#) of Informatics Europe:

- Informatik Austria (Austria)
- SIF – Société Informatique de France (France)
- FTI – Fakultätentag Informatik (Germany)
- GI – German Informatics Society (Germany)
- GRIN – GRuppo di INformatica (Italy)
- IPN - ICT-Research Platform Netherlands (Netherlands)
- CODDII – Conferencia de Directores y Decanos de Ingeniería Informática (Spain)
- SCIE – Sociedad Científica Informática de España (Spain)
- SIRA – Swiss Informatics Research Association (Switzerland)
- CPHC – Council of Professors and Heads of Computing (United Kingdom)

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